

SensApp

D1.9 Final plan for dissemination and exploitation

Grant Agreement Number	829104
Project Name	Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach
Project Acronym	SensApp
Start date of the project	01/01/2019
End date of the project	30/06/2022
Work package producing the document	WP1 – Management and dissemination
Deliverable identifier	D1.9
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead beneficiary	CNR
Contributors	All participants
Dissemination level	Public
Author	Veronica Vespini
Version	V1.0
Due date	Month 42
Delivery date	24/06/2022

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	
2. Scope and objectives of the deliverable.....	
3. Dissemination activities and channels.....	
3.1 The Corporate Identity.....	
3.2 Dissemination plan.....	
4. Exploitation plan.....	
5. Conclusion.....	

1. Introduction

Dissemination and exploitation plan refers to activities that are designed to ensure that the results of the project are appropriately recognized, demonstrated, and implemented on a large scale in, at least, 5 EU countries. Dissemination and exploitation activities are processes that will take place up to four years after the end of the project, as all project outputs will be put into practice and will be tested and piloted. This document is the last version (M42) of the Final Plan for dissemination and exploitation of SensApp project and is a part of WP1 - Management and dissemination. The content of the first deliverable D1.4 "First plan for dissemination and exploitation" included an overview of the concepts of Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation, their role in an H2020 project, and the relative strategies and action plans that the consortium would follow to promote the project, to foster the knowledge of its results and to ensure their uptake for future business opportunities. Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are all aimed to help maximize the impact of Research and Innovation actions. This final plan describes first the main communication and dissemination aspects that will be put into practice beyond the project and, secondly, the way in which of project outputs may be used in the future by consortium members, the public, scientific communities, and industrial stakeholders.

The global upheaval caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has shaped the working practices and decision-making processes of the SensApp consortium in dramatic ways, just after the first year of the project. In fact, most of the project (27 months over a total of 42 months) proceeded using only online collaboration as the primary mechanism for discussions ranging from technical details to principles of governance. The speed of organizational learning and innovation that was necessary in order to fulfill the original working plan was very challenging.

Moreover, the responsible person at Ginolis for contact, and governance changed on month 28, just during the execution of the Task 3.4, which was under their full responsibility. This produced significant issues for the reaction protocol which had to be implemented fully manually at CNR labs, without face-to-face cooperation with the other partners, thus delaying dramatically the final tests with body fluids. Nevertheless, significant know-how and new knowledge have been collected at CNR in the case of body fluids, also an alternative to plasma samples, that will be of fundamental importance for future collaborative actions aimed at continuing the SensApp activities, such as under the EIC Transition calls.

2. Scope and objectives of the deliverable

The main objective of the SensApp dissemination plan is to identify and plan the activities to be performed to transfer the findings and the results of the project and develop a response mechanism between the consortium and the various stakeholders to maximize the impact of SensApp. More in detail, this translates in a series of milestones to be met: the creation of public awareness of the project, the generation of interest within the scientific community, the direct involvement of stakeholders that can facilitate market up-take of the research results. The Dissemination manager will not be the only one involved in the dissemination actions. To ensure the effectiveness of the strategy and the accomplishments of the fixed goals, dissemination will be performed both as a collective activity managed by the entire consortium and, at the same time, as an individual set of actions carried out by each single partner on a local level. SensApp members comprise both

industrial and RTD partners who are well-established organizations that constitute a natural channel for the dissemination of the project and its results to other potential users.

SensApp dissemination actions will rely on the yearly experience, know-how and expertise of its members to ensure that project's output have had the necessary exposure to guarantee their utilization after the project is concluded. The plan for the dissemination activities is an iterative process that started from the outline of the deliverable D1.4 "First plan for dissemination and exploitation". The Dissemination strategy was drawn up in accordance with the stage of the development of the outputs of the project:

- a) Phase 1 (M1-M12): in this phase dissemination activities were oriented to the identification of interesting information sources and dissemination opportunities;
- b) Phase 2 (M13-M36): the consortium attended events of interest to disseminate preliminary project results and to start creating awareness and generating the interest of possible stakeholders;
- c) Phase 3 (M 36-M42): this phase is focused on the dissemination of the findings and results of the project to a more target audience for SensApp to facilitate the market take-up of the research outputs.

3. Dissemination activities and channels

3.1 The Corporate Identity

The compilation of the visual identity of the project is fundamental for the project dissemination, as it is highly recommended to use the professional corporate design in all material produced within the project to support an effect of recognition.

	Elements	Target group(s)
Corporate Identity (CI)	Logo/Website	All, i.e. it must still be attractively created for target groups
	Word document template	
	PowerPoint template	
	Brochures/Posters/Flyers	
The Consortium members used these templates to create a professional and easily recognizable identity of the project. All material was present on the internal part of the project website.		

Table 1: The elements of corporate identity.

SensApp Logo / website: Logo is of crucial importance to follow the rules of corporate identity given by the European Commission such as clear instructions on the use of logos. The SensApp website <http://www.sensapp.eu/> is the main tool for communication and dissemination. The language of the website is English, and it was launched at the beginning of the project. The website contains general information on the project, project objectives, partners' profiles, and the general framework within which the project is set. Specific emphasis was made on the research and on the results for dissemination. The public part of the website was regularly updated to feature project progress, short news, and participation in and setting of events. It contains links to other project channels

such as Twitter, YouTube, etc. Moreover, it is important to underline that the essential elements of a good communication and dissemination strategy is communication between Consortium Partners.

Figure1: SensApp website

Templates with the SensApp brand are prepared for partners' use:

- A4 letterhead consisting of a Microsoft Word template (and other open formats) using the header and footer areas of the document
- A PowerPoint presentation template to be used by all project partners containing SensApp logo, Horizon 2020 funding statement and EU flag, an indication of WP, partner organization, place and date of the event

Figure2: SensApp template

Any dissemination and visibility of results, including electronic forms, social must include the EU emblem and include the following text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 829104".

Brochures/Posters/Flyers: For concrete details on materials including brochures and flyers, please consult the deliverable D1.5 "Flyers with project targets and first results and promotional movie".

SensApp has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under agreement No 829104. www.sensapp.eu

3.2 Dissemination plan

The dissemination will be performed always complying with the conditions set forth in the CA and in other specific confidentiality agreements, in order to maintain confidentiality up to four years after the end of the project. All public results will be accessible from the project website and usable by all parties who may benefit from them to maximize the impact of the project. More details about the management of the intellectual property are included in the Deliverable D1.10.

In order to create visibility for the SensApp achievements and to ensure knowledge spillover and access to a broader public, we will use a broad variety of different dissemination channels:

- Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals (gold or green open access)
- Non-scientific publications
- Workshops
- Networking events and business fairs
- Project websites
- Communication material (e.g. posters, leaflets)
- Trade fairs and conferences
- Public events (e.g. European Research Night)
- Social media

The SensApp consortium will promote the publication of the results in peer-reviewed scientific journals and at scientific international conferences targeting relevant domains for the project, to reach the scientific community. The expected impact of presentations at this kind of event is very high because of the attendance of scientists and industrial stakeholders. In addition to the pure scientific papers, the results and impact of the SensApp project will be communicated to professionals, end-users, and industries through papers in technical bulletins and sectorial journals.

We are aware that in Horizon 2020 there is a mandate for beneficiaries to publish scientific research articles under the open-access models. However, this does not imply a general obligation to publish results and to neglect any related interest to the protection of results. We will consider both points before any decision to publish has been made. The decision on whether to protect any results will be paramount.

The SensApp team produced three **promotional videos** during the project execution. The first one showcases the project with general information about the consortium and objectives with also the basic technical and scientific details. The second one was prepared by Pulejo and targets primarily the clinical aspects of the project. The third one was prepared by VTT (Technical Research Centre of Finland, Ltd) and presents the SensApp demonstrator and brochure realized by the project. These videos have been uploaded on SensApp social channels (Facebook, Twitter, Youtube) and also on the Zenodo SensApp Community. They will represent a precious mean in the partners' hands for disseminating the SensApp objectives and outcomes at public events in a direct and synthetic way, to reach stakeholders' interest.

Flyer

1° Promotional video

Demonstrator Brochure

2° Promotional video

Demonstrator video

Figure3: Promotional videos

A **press release** was prepared during the second year of the project and was planned in Phase II of the project's dissemination and communication strategy to disseminate news and results of the project to media outlets (see figure below).

Press release

Figure4: Press release

Apart from publications targeting the scientific community, SensApp members prepared additional material to be used in events, **magazines** and **newspapers** able to attract a wide range of audiences (see figure below).

Kemia-Kemi, the main Finnish journal on chemistry

Italian magazines

Figure 5: Magazines and newspapers

During the project, the consortium actively disseminated the results through several **scientific publications**: the partners published at least 30 scientific publications in Scopus Indexed, peer-reviewed Journals and Conference Proceedings and they have participated in at least 20

SensApp has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under agreement No 829104. www.sensapp.eu

international conferences, moreover about 8 articles are in collaboration between the project partners. For the duration of project activities, such as meetings, conferences, workshops and similar, the partners were asked to produce photo and audio-visual material for it to be used during the project life cycle. All publications and accompanying data were stored in the online project community created on Zenodo. All uploads thus were directly indexed in OpenAIRE.

Figure6: International Conferences

SensApp project has been presented at different public events and we plan to continue applying this strategy for disseminating the outcomes of the project (see examples below).

Figure7: SensApp Dissemination

Thanks to the SensApp Project, it was possible to recruit University students to carry out an experimental **Master Thesis** and we will continue to propose thesis topics to young students related to SensApp research.

Master Thesis ... in collaboration with University of Naples Federico II

Figure8: Master Thesis

Social Media are currently the best way of diffusing information, probably with better visibility than a single website. Therefore, we will continue to hold SensApp social channels on Facebook, Twitter, and Youtube for disseminating project outcomes and for promoting the ongoing activities and events related to the project, after its end. In fact, the social media accounts will be constantly updated with the relevant news on project activities and events. Below are some monitoring data, all these communication materials were welcome by an increasing number of followers of the project's social media and helped to build a wider interested community on social media (twitter: 550 followers compared with 480 last middle year and 260 followers on Instagram compared with 147 last middle year).

Figure9: SensApp social media

In the Plan for Data Management (deliverable D1.3) there was a description of the management of all the data and data sets that were collected, processed, generated, and preserved during and after the project end, as well as the openness of the data to the public. According to the DMP we will follow these general principles in the dissemination of the project actions and results after the end of the project:

- There is open access to published data when not in conflict with IP protection issues (e.g. through Zenodo)
- The partners make use of the most appropriate community standards and best practices to manage the project data
- The privacy of personal data is respected by sharing it only with the EC in order to fulfill the project obligations, it is not publicly available
- Metadata is strategic in order to ensure the discoverability and access to the data

4. Exploitation plan

Exploitation measures are vital in Horizon 2020 and are used to maximize the potential of the funded activities so that the results are used beyond the lifetime of the project. Results should be tailored to the needs of others; transferrable to new areas; continuation after the end of the funding

period; or used to influence future policies and practices. According to the GA, each beneficiary must take measures, up to four years after the end of the project, aiming to ensure the exploitation of its results. Therefore, SensApp consortium members will evaluate the opportunity to exploit the results by different actions with the aim to profit from the potential marketing and commercialization of the intellectual assets acquired during the project. Details about the specific results obtained in SensApp are given in Deliverable D1.10.

The following main measures will be considered for next exploitation:

- To use research results in further research activities either internally and/or as background to be brought into a new collaborative research project (e.g. EIC Transition call), also broadening the field of application
- To license the patents that will be filed after the end of the project, both from individual partners and from joint ownership agreements (see details in D1.10)
- To evaluate the possibility to set up joint ventures, for example with companies working in the field of liquid micro-dispensing (e.g. Bio-Rad), to combine the know-how from the project with the company capital
- To promote SensApp topics in the academia through PhD and master students theses, as already performed during the execution of the project
- To consider the possibility for exploiting the results through setting up a Spin-off company

5. Conclusion

This document presented the consortium strategy for the dissemination, communication and exploitation for SensApp. It identified the projects objectives, tools, channels and overall strategies to efficiently communicate, disseminate and exploit towards the projects objectives and intended outputs.